

Implementation of Office Technology and Management Curriculum Towards Acquisition of Word Processing Skill

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Abstract

The research assessed the implementation of Office Technology and Management curriculum toward acquisition of word processing skills in Polytechnics in North-east Nigeria. Two specific purposes were determined and it was anchored on Edward Thorndike classical experiment theory. The study adopted explanatory mixed method research design. The population was 115 comprising 107 lecturers and 8 Heads of Office Technology and Management Departments from eight polytechnics in the North-east. It was a census study since the whole population was used. A 20-item questionnaire tagged 'Implementation of Office Technology and Management Curriculum towards Acquisition of Word Processing Skills' (IOTMCAWPS) with modified 4-points rating scale was the instrument used for the quantitative data collection. A semi-structured interview was used to collect the qualitative data. The instruments were face and content validated by three experts. The internal consistence of the instrument was determined using Cronbach Alpha procedure and the result yielded a reliability coefficient index of 0.82. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyze the data collected to answer the research questions, independent t-test and ANOVA were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed among others that demonstration, discovery, group discussion, inquiry method, activity-based method, and guided discovery as well as innovative method are methods of teaching necessary towards acquisition of word processing skills (mean = 2.89, SD = 0.75). The findings also reveals test, quiz, presentation, group project, hands-on activity, and diagnostic assessment as well as summative assessment are utilized in the acquisition of keyboarding and word processing skills (=3.17, SD 0.69). The findings on all the two hypotheses tested revealed that there were significant differences in the mean ratings of lecturers and instructors and lecturers based on their year of experiences ($t_{105} = 12.769, P < 0.05, t_{105} = 6.180, P < 0.05$). Sequel to the findings of the study it was recommended among others that heads of departments and units should ensure proper supervision of lecturers implementing this course so that the right pedagogy is utilized for the acquisition of keyboarding and word processing skill.

Keywords: *Implementation, Office Technology and Management, Curriculum, Acquisition, Word processing, Skill.*

Introduction

The employment situation today is different, it is unlike the past when candidates were employed immediately after graduation. In an effort to find lasting solution to the challenges of unemployment, there has been series of review of the educational policies and curriculum which is aimed at job creation. The review is also aimed at self-employment, acquisition of appropriate skills that could be transformed to economic, social, physical and mental competencies, and to contribute to the development of the nation (Amahi, & Odigili 2021). OTM programme which is a branch of business education, trains learners to acquire skills for business and about business for social and economic transformation (Okoro, 2015; Ijarshar & Ayidiowu, 2015; Enwemasor, 2016). When the secretarial nomenclature changed to Office Manager, it was an improvement in the curriculum to make the recipients of the programme more relevant after graduation. According to Umoru and Nguwap (2021), the advent of ICT led to a comprehensive review of the secretarial studies curriculum, resulting in its evolution into OTM. Technological trends have caused OTM curriculum planners to reduce credit hours of courses that are not technologically related. Much emphasis is now laid on technological courses, as it is believed that skills acquired in these courses are more relevant for survival.

The effort is to ensure that learners acquire skills for establishment of personal businesses so as to reduce unemployment and contribute to the Nigerian society. Curriculum implementers should make this a reality by teaching students skills that ensure their survival in the contemporary world. If OTM curriculum implementers realise that word processing is a course that can enable graduates to be self-reliant, then they will put great effort in teaching this skilled course. The course should be taught with firmness, enforcing students to do the

right thing will aid in the correction of the bad habits of learning word processing which students have formed. According to Baba and Akarahu (2014), OTM is a comprehensive term referring to those aspects of the educational process involving, in addition to general education, the study of technologies and related science and the acquisition of practical skills, attitudes, understanding and knowledge relating to occupations in various sectors of economic and social life. The primary goal of OTM is to graduate competent, skilful and dynamic students that will serve as office managers, administrators, businessmen and women who will effectively compete in the world of work (Ibrahim, 2015). It means that OTM training is the sum total of knowledge, skill and attitude that are required for successful business.

OTM is a veritable course of study which builds her learners for positive contribution to national development. This implies that learners must possess office skills that will enable them to be globally relevant in office administration after graduation. It is for this reason that OTM programme is seen as a combination of courses concerned with the acquisition, development and inculcation of the proper work values and skills for global relevance of the individual (Olayinka, Asonibare & Oluwalola, 2021). The National Policy on Education (2013) listed the general objective of OTM course to include among others: to provide the orientation and basic skills with which to start a business; to provide basic business skills for personal use now and in the future; to prepare students for further training in business education; to relate the knowledge and skills to national development and to develop basic skills in office occupation.

Curriculum in education is generally defined as the entirety of students experiences that takes place in the educational process. It is often taken to be a planned succession of didactics, or a perspective of the students experiences in terms of the educator's school

pedagogical goals. Curriculum is the delivery of the components of an institution's educational mission, values, and theory of learning. It means that curriculum involves setting a particular programme that learners have to pass through to attain a certain level of knowledge. In any field of education curriculum must be seen as the reconstruction of knowledge and experiences, systematic development with the guidance of the school or relevant agencies which will enhance learners and the society's well-being (Osawaru & Okungbowa, 2014). Educators are concerned with everything about the curriculum right from the planning to the implementation stages. To this end, it can be deduced that education has not taken place when the curriculum is not properly implemented. Umoru (2019) supports this view when he states that achieving an ideal business education curriculum should not be viewed as an event but a continuous cycle that requires relevant curriculum mapping, interpretation, implementation and review. To ensure a stable economy, students (youths) that are believed to be the future leaders of the country, ought to be well equipped with basic skills to drive the economy.

Skill acquisition is the science that underpins movement, learning and execution and is more commonly termed motor learning and control. Skill acquisition is the means by which man adjust to life. There are basically three stages of skill acquisition; the cognitive stage, associative stage, and the autonomous stage. The first stage is when a person is still battling with the skill, the second is when individuals practice the skill, and the third is when they are already experts in the skill. This means that word processing skills acquisition involve cognitive, affective and psychomotor learning. Skill according to Umeano and Oguejifor (2020), has impact on the productivity and economy of a nation because of its integral part of development of human resources, thereby raising the productivity of workers and increasing their earning. In organizations workers give in skill in exchange for remuneration. Mshelia

(2019) in support of this states that if the skill or cluster of skills popularly referred to as aptitudes given is satisfactory both the staff and the employer will be satisfied at the end.

Word processing skills are critical elements in office studies and functions. The acquisition of word processing skills enable students prepare for the world of work, either as modern office workers or as self-employed personnel. Acquiring appropriate knowledge of the course enables graduates of the programme to be skilful. Word processing skill can be acquired in different ways through teaching and learning. Word processing skill is the competence in the performance of specific tasks after a period of training or experience. This skill enables the graduate to be grammatically perfect. According to Amesi (2017), word processing skill acquisition is a deliberate, systematic and sustained efforts which lead to capability that makes a person effectively and efficiently perform activities or jobs involving cognitive, technical and interpersonal dispositions. Word processing skill is acquired through learning that leads to competence that enhances better performance of tasks and enable a person to contribute to societal growth and development (Gidado & Daramola, 2021). Word processing skill enables the graduate to effectively process documents without error. It is the ability to produce correct document. It is a course that teaches rapid and efficient processing, storage and printing of linguistic data for composition and editing. Word processing skill is a very important skill to office manager because the skill enhances the development of accurate document.

A good office manager must be effective in word processing since this skill is used in the office both in attending to customers and in producing accurate documents. An office manager who is not efficient in word processing cannot be a good entrepreneur. Word processing is a major course in OTM that always go with the technological trends because most of the technological machines have linguistic words which are processed effectively to

equip the students for the modern office. In fact, word processing skills equip the graduate for survival in this unemployment age. Inalegwu (2016) views skill as expertness, aptitude and competence appropriate for a certain job; it has to do with expert knowledge and originitive reasoning to the level of mastery. The author stressed that students have to acquire initial training or knowledge related to the assignment to be performed through formal, informal or a combination of the two.

The paper is anchored on Thorndike 1898 behaviourism theory, practice is essential from a behaviorist perspective, people are more likely to understand when they have the opportunity to behave for example, when they can type, write, try out, or exhibit. Ideally, students should participate throughout the learning process, rather than supply inactive role of whatever information or skill being taught. Students should confront academic subject matter in a convinced mood and consociate it with positive emotions. The enduringness and generalization of some definitive responses point to the need for a positivistic classroom environment for students. When students face academic subjects with confident, they are more likely to pursue it of their own accord. Curriculum implementers have always disputed that school should be a place where a student achieves more success than failure, and classical conditioning provides a justification for the argument.

In the view of Umoru and Haruna (2018) demonstration method involves showing, doing or telling the students the point of emphasis. The authors state that this method is majorly used as a technique within a particular method of curriculum implementation and sometimes as a method of teaching itself. The duty of the implementer in this method is to illustrate to students how to do something (s) or principles first by explanation of the nature of the act verbally to students and then followed by demonstrating the act in a systematic manner and afterwards the students repeat the act. The group discussion teaching method is

designed to provide opportunity for discourse between teacher and students and within students themselves. The method centres on shared conversations, discussions and exchange of ideas in the classroom. According to Ojo (2011), this method provides the privilege for both the teacher and students to sit and listen as well as talk and think thus, emphasising the procedure of knowing as valuable as knowing the right answer. Okolocha, Ile and Okolocha (2012) emphasised that teaching methods when properly matched with the objectives of the course of the study, helps to stimulate students active learning through reflective thinking in areas of discussion, seeing, writing and doing as students go through the course contents with the teacher as the facilitator.

Okoye and Umezuluike (2014) viewed assessment as an omnibus term, which includes all the processes and products which will describe the nature and the extent of children's learning, its degree of correspondence with the aims and objectives of teaching and its relationship with the environment designed to facilitate learning. Onuorah (2016) upheld that assessment of learners is the process of gathering information about how learners are progressing in their learning. Amobi (2019) views continuous assessment as a systematic and objective process of determining the extent of a student's performance in all the expected changes in the student's behaviour, from the day the student begins to undertake a course of study and a judicious accumulation of all pieces of information derived from this purpose with a view to using the information to guide and shape the student and to serve as basis for making important decisions about the child. Emeasoba (2016) asserts that the success of a school in achieving its goal is largely dependent on the teachers and the process of teaching and learning. The author maintained that assessment in teaching-learning is any assessment for which the first precedence in its design and practice is to serve the purpose of promoting students learning.

Statement of the Problem

Office technology education is expected to equip recipients with work based skills that will enable them to be self-employed and employers of labour. Like any other educational programme the implementation of the curriculum is very important to the effectiveness and achievement of goals of the programme. It is observed that many graduates of OTM can hardly operate the word processor and therefore, are not employed. The command of English is very essential to an office manager as it is used to encourage customer patronage. First impression matters in organization and the office manager's rapport with customers encourages customers. It has been observed that lack of training on new curriculum and poor staff development is an issue in curriculum implementation and acquisition of skill. Methods of teaching and assessment practices were observed to be part of the problems. The researcher observed also that most employers of labour are not satisfied with OTM graduates performance in the office. In support of this Oludare and Adajare (2019), report that OTM graduates are not able to gain employment in various organizations as a result of incompetence which is traceable to the quality of education given to the graduates. This elicited enquiry on the possible reasons for this development, as against the usual practice of word processing mastery embedded in rapid and efficient processing, storage and printing of linguistic data for composition and editing. If this study is ignored students will persist on slow processing method and the satisfaction embedded in efficient processing, storage and printing of linguistic data for composition and editing of words will be lost. Also, organizations will lack proficient secretaries in the future. It is therefore, penitent to study the implementation of OTM curriculum towards the acquisition of word processing skills.

Purpose of the Study

The major purpose of the study is to determine the implementation of Office Technology and Management curriculum towards acquisition of word processing skills in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. examine the methods of implementation of OTM curriculum towards the acquisition of word processing skills.
4. investigate the assessment practices for the implementation of OTM curriculum towards the acquisition of word processing skills.

Research Questions

This research provided answers to the following research questions.

1. What are the methods of implementation of OTM curriculum towards the acquisition of keyboarding and word processing skills?
2. What are the assessment practices for the implementation of OTM curriculum towards the acquisition of keyboarding and word processing skills?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated in line with the specific purposes of the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

- Ho₁. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers and instructors on the methods of implementation of OTM curriculum towards the acquisition of keyboarding and word processing skills.
- Ho₂. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers based on their experiences on the assessment practices utilized for the implementation of OTM curriculum towards the acquisition of keyboarding and word processing skills.

Methods

The study adopted a mixed method research design. The Explanatory Confirmation research design was employed for the study. The mixed research design is suitable for this study since data was collected through quantitative and qualitative methods which will complement each other. The population of the study for the quantitative data comprises 107 OTM lecturers in Polytechnics in North-East, Nigeria. The population include, four Federal and four State polytechnics that offer Office Technology and Management programme in North-East Nigeria. For the qualitative data, all the eight Heads of Departments in these polytechnics were involved bringing the total population of the study to 115 OTM curriculum implementers. Due to the manageable size of the population, the entire 115 OTM lecturers were involved in the study. The research instruments were structured questionnaire and semi-structured interview developed by the researcher after extensive review of literature. The 20-item questionnaire was titled ‘Implementation of Office Technology and Management Curriculum on Acquisition of Word Processing Skills (IOTMCAWPS).’ The Questionnaire was structured on a modified 4-point Likert scale of Strongly Agreed, Agreed, Disagreed, and Strongly Disagreed with corresponding values of 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. The second instrument is the interview schedule which was used to collect the qualitative data.

The instruments were face and content validated by three experts. Two from the Department of Business and Entrepreneurship Education Kwara State University, Malete and one from Department of Measurement and Evaluation Taraba State University, Jalingo. The corrections, suggestions, modifications and restructuring made by the experts were incorporated to produce the final copy of the instruments. The researcher conducted a pilot study at the Federal Polytechnic Offa. The data generated from the pilot study were analysed using Cronbach Alpha reliability method to determine the internal consistency of the

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instrument. The Cronbach coefficient calculated for this study was 0.82. The quantitative data was collected by the researcher with the help of one research assistant from each of the polytechnics under study. The interviews were conducted face-to-face and through (WhatsApp). Mean and Standard Deviation were employed to analyse the data collected to answer the research questions. The data collected from the interview was analysed using content analysis. The null hypotheses were tested using t-test and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) at 0.05 level of significance at the relevant degree of freedom. Decision rule with respect to research questions was based on the principle of upper and lower limits of the mean. Thus:

Response Options	Points	Real Limit of Numbers
Strongly Agreed	4	3.50 – 4.00
Agreed	3	2.50 – 3.49
Disagreed	2	1.50 – 2.49
Strongly Disagreed	1	1.00 – 1.49

Any item with standard deviation of less than 1.96 indicates that there is not much variability from the mean or from the responses of the respondents. On the other hand, any standard deviation above 1.96 indicates that there are wide variations in the responses of the respondents. For the hypotheses any null hypothesis whose p-value is equal or greater than the Alpha value ($0.05 \geq$) and at the derived degree of freedom was retained and concluded that there is no significant difference between the respondents otherwise it was rejected.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the methods of implementation of OTM curriculum towards the acquisition of word processing skills?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of responses on the methods of implementation of

OTM curriculum towards the acquisition of word processing skills				
S/N	Item Statements	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1.	Demonstration method of teaching is utilized in the acquisition of word processing skills	3.45	0.50	Agreed
2.	Field Trip method of teaching is utilized in the acquisition of word processing skills	2.19	0.90	Disagreed
3.	Discovery method of teaching is utilized in the acquisition of word processing skills	3.18	0.74	Agreed
4.	Group discussion method of teaching is utilized in the acquisition of word processing skills	3.15	0.64	Agreed
5.	Dalton instruction method of teaching is utilized in the acquisition of word processing skills	2.15	0.83	Disagreed
6.	Socratic instruction method of teaching is utilized in the acquisition of word processing skills	2.08	0.81	Disagreed
7.	Inquiry method of teaching is utilized in the acquisition of word processing skills	3.40	0.66	Agreed
8.	Activity-based method of teaching is utilized in the acquisition of word processing skills	3.24	0.80	Agreed
9.	Guided discovery method of instruction is utilized in the acquisition of word processing skills	3.00	0.82	Agreed
10.	Innovative method of teaching is utilized in the acquisition of word processing skills	3.09	0.76	Agreed
Weighted average		2.89	0.75	Agreed

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Analysis of data in Table 1 shows mean and standard deviation of responses on the methods of implementation of OTM curriculum towards the acquisition of word processing skills. The table reveals that the respondents agreed that demonstration, discovery, and group discussion methods are methods of teaching utilized in the acquisition of word processing skills (mean = 3.45, 3.18 and 3.15 respectively). In addition, the respondents agreed that inquiry method, activity-based method, and guided discovery as well as innovative method are methods of teaching utilized in the acquisition of word processing skills (mean = 3.40, 3.24, 3.00 and 3.09 respectively). Table 1 also reveals the respondents' disagreement to field trip method, Dalton instruction method and Socratic instruction method as methods of

teaching utilized in the acquisition of word processing skills (mean = 2.19, 2.15 and 2.08 respectively).

All the 10 item constructs have standard deviation ranging from 0.50 to 0.90 which means that the responses of the respondents are not widely spread as they are close to their respective mean scores. The table shows a grand calculated weighted average mean and standard deviation scores of 2.89 and 0.75 respectively.

Research Question 2: What are the assessment practices for the implementation of OTM curriculum towards the acquisition of word processing skills?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of responses on the assessment practices for the implementation of OTM curriculum towards the acquisition of word processing skills

S/N	Item Statements	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1.	Test is utilized in the acquisition of word processing skills	3.38	0.68	Agreed
2.	Take home assignment is utilized in the acquisition of word processing skills	3.52	0.50	Strongly agreed
3.	Classwork is utilized in the acquisition of word processing skills	3.50	0.50	Strongly agreed
4.	Quiz is utilized in the acquisition of word processing skills	2.76	0.72	Agreed
5.	Presentation is utilized in the acquisition of word processing skills	3.01	0.83	Agreed
6.	Examination is utilized in the acquisition of word processing skills	3.51	0.54	Strongly agreed
7.	Group project is utilized in the acquisition of word processing skills	3.02	0.80	Agreed
8.	Hands-on activity is utilized in the acquisition of word processing skills	3.23	0.71	Agreed
9.	Diagnostic assessment is utilized in the acquisition of word processing skills	2.49	0.90	Agreed
10.	Summative assessment is utilized in the acquisition of word processing skills	3.28	0.72	Agreed
Weighted average		3.17	0.69	Agreed

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Analysis of data in Table 2 shows mean and standard deviation of responses on the assessment practices for the implementation of OTM curriculum towards the acquisition of

word processing skills. The table reveals that the respondents agreed that test is utilized in the acquisition of word processing skills, same way quiz, presentation, Group project, hands-on activity, and diagnostic assessment as well as summative assessment are utilized in the acquisition of word processing skills. These were supported by mean scores of 3.38, 2.76, 3.01, 3.02, 3.23, 3.49 and 3.28 respectively. In addition, the respondents strongly agreed that take home assignment, classwork and examination are utilized in the acquisition of word processing skills. These were supported by mean scores of 3.52, 3.50, and 3.51 respectively.

All the 10 item constructs have standard deviation ranging from 0.50 to 0.90 which means that the responses of the respondents are not widely spread as they are close to their respective mean scores. Table 2 therefore reveals that the respondents unanimously agreed to all the constructs as the mean scores are far above 2.50. The table shows a grand calculated weighted average mean and standard deviation scores of 3.17 and 0.69 respectively.

Test of Hypotheses

Ho₁. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers and instructors on methods of implementation of OTM curriculum towards the acquisition of word processing skills.

Table 3: Summary of t-test of the difference between lecturers and instructors on methods of implementation of OTM curriculum towards the acquisition of word processing skills

Group	N	Mean	SD	t-cal	Df	p-value	Decision
Lecturers	74	3.13	0.64				
				6.180	105	0.000	H ₀₃ Rejected
Instructors	33	2.37	0.45				

Source: Field Survey, 2023

P<0.05

The data in Table 3 reveal that there are 74 OTM lecturers and 33 OTM instructors. The responses of OTM lecturers indicates that they rated the methods of implementation higher ($\bar{x} = 3.13$; SD = 0.64) than OTM instructors ($\bar{x} = 2.37$; SD = 0.45). Their responses

are close to the mean as the standard deviations are very low. The table reveals that there was significant difference in the responses of lecturers and instructors on methods of implementation of OTM curriculum towards the acquisition of word processing skills ($t_{105} = 6.180, P < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that lecturers and instructors differ significantly in their responses regarding the methods of implementation of OTM curriculum towards the acquisition of word processing skills.

Ho₂. There is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers based on their experiences on the assessment practices utilized for the implementation of OTM curriculum towards the acquisition of word processing skills

Table 4: Summary of ANOVA result showing difference in the mean ratings of lecturers based on their experiences on the assessment practices

Senatorial Districts	Number	Mean (\bar{x})	SD
Experienced	30	3.90	0.13
More experienced	55	3.11	0.31
Highly experienced	22	2.33	0.42

Sources	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Between Groups	31.501	2	0.074			
Within Groups	9.523	104	0.291	172.015	0.000	Ho ₄ Rejected
Total	41.024	106				

Source: Field Survey, 2023

The descriptive statistics (frequency, mean and standard deviation) as presented on table 4 shows experienced, more experienced and highly experienced have means of 3.90, 3.11, and 2.33 and corresponding standard deviation of 0.13, 0.31, 0.42 respectively. The result of analysis of variance as presented in Table 4 reveals that the calculated value of F is

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172.015 ($F_{2,104} = 172.015$) and the observed probability value is 0.000 which is less than the fixed probability value of 0.05 ($P < 0.05$). This indicates that the null hypotheses which stated that, there is no significant difference in the mean responses of lecturers based on their experiences on the assessment practices utilized for the implementation of OTM curriculum towards the acquisition of word processing skills was rejected. This implied that lecturers based on their experiences differ in their responses regarding assessment practices utilized for the implementation of OTM curriculum towards the acquisition of word processing skills.

Analysis of Qualitative Data

The qualitative data were analysed using content analysis and the identified themes are related to the purpose of the study since the interview was semi-structured.

Methods of Teaching

The HODs said that lecturers utilizes almost all the teaching methods in the implementation of OTM curriculum for acquisition of word processing skills. According to the Heads of the Department, the conventional methods like the demonstration, discussion, presentation, lecture, enquiry, brainstorming, instruction methods and so on are utilized in the teaching for acquisition of skills. All the HODs said the lecturers hardly use the field trip method of teaching where the students are exposed to some of the facilities that may not be available in the departments and how to use the facilities because of paucity of funds. A HOD said the lecturers in his department utilize both the theory and practical method in order to give wider knowledge of the courses to the students. In the practical aspect they give students functional projects and group them to work on the projects. Another Head of Department said some lecturers are not conversant with some of the modern teaching facilities like the projector. He said it is important to use the projector because from time to time using the projector in certain aspects of teaching makes understanding easier.

Assessment Practices

The qualitative data collected on assessment practices for the implementation of Office Technology and Management curriculum towards acquisition of word processing skills reveals that all the eight participants representing 100% of the participants said that students are evaluated through test, assignment, take home assignment, presentation, classwork and examination for the acquisition of word processing skills. One of the Head of Department said that there is nonchalant attitude on the side of the students because of these students are always advised to make intensive use of the typing pool and computer labs during their leisure time so that they can have enough time to practice in order to acquire skills.

However, another Head of a Department said that the assessment practices are in place but sometimes are not adequately utilized by some lecturers. He said a lecturer will tell the HOD that he/she has completed his/her continuous assessment but when you see the content of what the lecturer has given to the students as an assessment it is not adequate for the acquisition of skills based on the content of the course.

Discussion of Findings

The study was on the implementation of office technology and management curriculum towards the acquisition of word processing skills in Polytechnics in North East, Nigeria. The findings concerning research question one revealed that lecturers and HODs of OTM departments in North-east Nigeria, agreed that demonstration, discovery, group discussion, inquiry, activity-based and guided discovery as well as innovative methods are methods of teaching utilized in the acquisition of word processing skills. The findings also, revealed that field trip method, Dalton instruction method and Socratic instruction methods are not utilized in the acquisition of word processing skills. This shows that lecturers

demonstrated high level of support for most of the teaching methods used in the acquisition of word processing skills. These findings corroborate with the study of Ojo (2011) who states that most effective methods in the teaching of skills and performance-oriented subjects in Office Technology and Management is demonstration method. The teachers using demonstration method explain steps in operations and techniques of handling office technologies in work stations and learning environments. Umoru and Haruna (2018) affirmed that demonstration method involves showing, doing or telling the students the point of emphasis.

Okolocha, Ile and Okolocha (2012) were in consonance with this view when they emphasized that teaching methods when properly matched with the objectives of the course of the study, help to stimulate students active learning through reflective thinking in areas of discussion, seeing, writing and doing as students go through the course contents with the teacher as the facilitator. The null hypothesis that states that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of lecturers and instructors on the methods of implementation of OTM curriculum towards acquisition of word processing skills in polytechnics in North-east was rejected.

The next findings on research purpose, questions and hypothesis 2 which revealed that OTM lecturers in Polytechnics in North-east agreed that test, quiz, presentation, group project, hands-on activity, and diagnostic assessment, summative assessment, take home assignment, classwork and examination are assessment practices utilized. Both the quantitative and qualitative analyses of the data collected to answer this research question are in support of all the items under the assessment practices for the acquisition of word processing skills. These findings are in line with that of Amobi (2019) who remarked that the Federal Ministry of Education outlined major provisions of continuous assessment in her

handbook on continuous assessment as guidelines which teachers must carry out for proper implementation of continuous assessment. Emeasoba (2016) corroborated this view by stating that formative assessment is carried out informally or formally in daily classroom learning and teaching throughout the school term and year. These findings also, corroborate with the studies of Okoye and Umezuluike (2014) and Onuorah (2016) who suggested that comprehensiveness of continuous assessment means that it is not focused on academic skills alone, it embraces the cognitive, the psychomotor and the affective domains.

The findings also showed that there was significant difference between the mean ratings of lecturers on assessment practices utilized. Therefore, the null hypothesis that states that there is no significant difference in the mean ratings of lecturers based on their experiences on the assessment practices utilized in the implementation of OTM curriculum towards the acquisition of word processing skills was rejected.

Conclusion

The conclusions are made based on the findings which revealed that acquisition of word processing skills is very much important to office managers in the modern office. The presence of technology has changed the face of the office and the duties performed in the office therefore, office managers must be efficient in word processing to meet with the technological demand. This is necessary because the contemporary education requires learners to be skilled to enable graduates to be self-employed in order to curb the dearth of unemployment. Word processing skills will always be used in the offices because secretaries proficiency in word processing enhances organizational productivity.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were advanced to channel the way forward:

1. Heads of departments and units should ensure proper supervision of lecturers implementing

this course so that the right pedagogy is utilized for the acquisition of word processing skills.

2. The different assessment practices should be utilized by the curriculum implementer in assessing the students especially those that will allow the implementer to observe the students rate of progress in the acquisition of skills.

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